

“NOUN AND ITS USAGE IN A SENTENCE”

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada asosan, otlarning turlari, ko‘plik shakli va ularning yasalishi, gapda qo‘yilish tartibi haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Key words: Noun, plural, singular, common nouns, proper nouns, countable, uncountable, collective nouns, material nouns.

What is the noun?

A group of words that is an answer to the question "who?" and "what?" is called a noun

Nouns are usually preceded by articles and prepositions.

For example: a table, the table, on the table.

Nouns can be used in singular and plural: a book- books, a letter-letters.

Shaxs yoki buyumni ifodalovchi kim? va nima? shoira javob bo‘luvchi so‘zlar ot so‘z turkumi deyiladi

In English nouns are divided into common nouns and proper nouns. Names of individual persons or things are proper nouns.

For example: Toshkent, The Volga, Olimov.

Common names of the same kind of things are considered common nouns: a boy, a girl.

As we all know that nouns in English are divided into the following groups:

a) Collective nouns that represent a person or group of animals: a family-families, a crowd- crowds.

b) Material nouns represent substances: water, steel, gold.

c) Abstract nouns represent sign, action, state, feeling, appearance, science, art, honesty, bravery, darkness, love, music etc.

Endi biz otlarni sanaladigan va sanalmaydigan otlar guruhiga ajratib o‘rganamiz. Sanaladigan otlarni sanab bo‘ladi. Ular birlik va ko‘plikda ishlatiladi.

I have bought two books.

Material and Abstract nouns are uncountable nouns. Uncountable nouns can be used alone.

She does not eat rice.

O‘zbek tili kabi ingliz tilida ham sanalmaydigan otlar mavjud bo‘lib, biz ularni sanay olmaymiz. Masalan, biz ona tilimizda ikkita non, bitta sovun, mebellar deb sanay olamiz, ammo ingliz tilida bundan mustasno holatda qo‘llaniladi:

Accommodation- turar-joy

Luggage- yuk, bagaj

Money- pul

News- yangilik

Otlar haqida umumiy ma‘lumotga ega bo‘ldik. Endi ingliz tilida ularning ko‘plik shakli qanday yasalishiga e‘tibor berib o‘tamiz.

The singular form of nouns refers to one thing or person: a pen, a book.

The plural form of nouns represent two or more things: windows, doors.

The plural form of nouns in English is slightly different from Uzbek. In English nouns are made plural by adding -s to them.

The suffix -es is added to nouns ending with the letters -s, -ss, -x, -ch, -sh.

Class- classes, dish- dishes, box- boxes

The suffix -s is added to nouns ending with the letters -se, -ce, -ze, -ge.

Horse- horses, prize- prizes, place-places.

The plural of some nouns changes from the stem without adding an suffix.

Man - men - erkaklar

Woman - women- ayollar

Goose - geese- g'ozlar

Mouse - mice - sichqonlar

Child - children - bolalar

Foot - feet - oyoqlar

Most compound nouns are only used in the plural form:

Scissors - qaychi

Spectacles - ko'zoynak

Trousers - shim

Scales - tarozi

My trousers are too tight.

The following Collective nouns are also used only in the plural.

Goods - mollar, tovarlar

Proceeds - savdo tushumi

Contents - mundarija

Clothes - kiyimlar

Ammo bir qancha mustasno holatlarni ham kuzatishimiz mumkin. People so'zi odamlar ma'nosida kelganda faqat ko'plikda ishlatiladi, ammo xalq ma'nosida birlikda ham ko'plikda ham ishlatilishi mumkin.

There were a lot of people at the party.

The Uzbek people have experienced many difficulties.

In conclusion, the subject of noun is very comprehensive. This article provides information about the plural form of the noun in which case it is used and the order of its formation in the sentences.

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